

Computation of excess Gibbs free energy of activation, Grunberg-Nissan interaction parameter and rheochor for binary solutions at different temperatures

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Abstract : The values of excess Gibbs free energy of activation of viscous flow, Grunberg-Nissan interaction parameter and rheochor for sixteen binary solutions at different temperatures have been computed. Nature of intermolecular interactions occurring in these solutions has been predicted on the basis of aforementioned properties.

Keywords : Excess property, interaction parameter, Gibbs free energy, binary solutions.

Accurate knowledge of thermodynamic mixing properties¹⁻³ such as excess volume, excess enthalpy and excess Gibbs free energy of binary solutions are important in theoretical and applied areas of research. The data of these excess properties are useful in practical purpose for the design of mixing, storage and process equipment in chemical industry. For relating excess volume and excess enthalpy, the data of excess Gibbs free energy are required. These are also required for use by the chemists in many practical problems concerning mass transport^{4,5} and fluid flow. Moreover, for understanding the intermolecular interactions^{3,4} in binary solutions considerable interest has been developed in recent years for the study of excess thermodynamic properties. In literature, few attempts⁴⁻⁸ have been made to study excess properties of binary solutions.

In the present paper, the values of Grunberg-Nissan interaction parameter, excess Gibbs free energy of activation of viscous flow and rheochor for various binary solutions viz. *n*-hexane + α -pinene, *n*-hexane + β -pinene, *n*-hexane + *p*-cymene, *n*-hexane + *S*(-)-limonene, *n*-hexane + 1,8-cineole, *n*-hexane + linalool, 2-methyl-propan-2-ol + nitromethane at 298.15 K, methanol + nitromethane, ethanol + nitromethane, propan-1-ol + nitromethane, propan-2-ol + nitromethane, butan-2-ol + nitromethane, 2-methyl-propan-2-ol + nitromethane at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K, diethylene glycol diethyl ether (DEGDEE) + 1-propanol, diethylene glycol dibu-

tyl ether (DEGDBE) + 1-propanol at 288.15, 298.15 and 308.15 K, *N*-methylacetamide + 2-methoxyethanol, *N*-methylacetamide + water at 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K have been calculated.

The data required for this purpose have been collected from different sources^{2,8-10}. To the best of our knowledge, the values of Grunberg-Nissan interaction parameter, excess Gibbs free energy of the activation of viscous flow and rheochor for binary solutions at different temperatures under the present investigation are not found in literature.

The binary solutions selected for the present study are important due to useful components constituting these solutions. For example, α -pinene is successfully used in asymmetric reduction for synthesizing optically pure materials with chiral organoboranes¹¹. *N*-Methylacetamide is a strongly hydrogen bonded, highly structured, protic and basic solvent while 2-methoxyethanol and water are commonly used solvents. Also, nitromethane is an aprotic solvent with high polarity useful in a variety of applications. Polyethers are important industrial solvents. Moreover, alcohols are the most well-known solvents with protic and self-associated properties, which are useful in the study of hydrophobic effects. Besides these, alcohols of varying chain lengths upon mixing with nitromethane generate interesting properties due to specific interactions². Pine resins and essential oils are mostly used in the pharmaceutical, cosmetic and perfume industries¹².

Theoretical :

Grunberg-Nissan¹³ interaction parameter, d^l , the Gibbs free energy of activation of viscous flow, G^{*E} and rheochor, R , were calculated respectively from eqs. (1) to (3).

$$\ln \eta = x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2 + x_1 x_2 d^l \quad (1)$$

$$G^{*E} = RT \left[\ln (V\eta) - \sum_{i=1}^2 x_i \ln (V_i \eta_i) \right] \quad (2)$$

$$R = V \cdot \eta^{1/8} \quad (3)$$

where x , η and V respectively are the mole fraction, the dynamic viscosity and the molar volume. The subscript 'i' represents the pure components and R and T are the gas constant and the absolute temperature respectively.

Results and discussion

Grunberg-Nissan interaction parameter, d^l , excess Gibbs free energy of the activation of viscous flow, G^{*E} and rheochor, R , for the binary systems under the present investigation have been calculated using eqs. (1) to (3). The values of density and viscosity for binary solutions under the present investigation at different temperatures are taken from literature^{2,8-10}.

Grunberg-Nissan¹³ interaction parameter is regarded as measure of the strength of interactions between the mixing species⁴. Fort and Moore¹⁴ and Ramamoorthy¹⁵ reported that for any binary liquid system, the positive value of d^l indicates the presence of strong interactions and the negative value of d^l indicates the presence of weak interactions between the components. Negative values of d^l indicate a positive deviation from Raoult's law¹³ and support the idea of the formation of dispersion force as intermolecular interaction between unlike molecules. The results of computation reveal that the values of d^l are negative over entire composition range for almost all the binary solutions under investigation except three solutions (*n*-hexane + *S*(-)-limonene, *N*-methylacetamide + 2-methoxyethanol and *N*-methylacetamide + water). Positive values of d^l are found for binary solution of *N*-methylacetamide with 2-methoxyethanol in the *N*-methylacetamide rich region of compositions. Thus, weak interactions between the component molecules are present in all binary solutions except three solutions mentioned earlier, where strong interactions are found. A close perusal of results obtained theoretically shows that the excess Gibbs free energy of activation of viscous flow (G^{*E}) is negative for all the investigated binary solutions at different temperatures, except four binary solutions (*n*-

hexane + *S*(-)-limonene, DEGDBE + 1-propanol, *N*-methylacetamide + 2-methoxyethanol and *N*-methylacetamide + water) where positive values are found. The positive value of G^{*E} shows the presence of strong interaction and the negative value of G^{*E} indicates the presence of weak interaction between the component molecules. Strong specific interactions are responsible for positive G^{*E} values in binary solutions viz. *n*-hexane + *S*(-)-limonene, DEGDBE + 1-propanol, *N*-methylacetamide + 2-methoxyethanol and *N*-methylacetamide + water.

It has also been observed that on increasing the temperature the values of G^{*E} increase for butan-2-ol + nitromethane, DEGDEE + 1-propanol, DEGDBE + 1-propanol and *N*-methylacetamide + 2-methoxyethanol and it decreases for methanol + nitromethane and *N*-methylacetamide + water systems. However, an increase in temperature decreases the values of G^{*E} and after a certain temperature increment it starts increasing in the case of binary solutions of nitromethane with ethanol, propan-1-ol, propan-2-ol and 2-methyl-propan-2-ol. It is also clear from the results that the values of G^{*E} decrease with increase in chain length of alkanols investigated in the present study.

The calculated values of rheochor decrease with increase in mole fraction of *n*-hexane in binary solutions viz. *n*-hexane + α -pinene, *n*-hexane + β -pinene, *n*-hexane + *p*-cymene, *n*-hexane + *S*(-)-limonene, *n*-hexane + 1,8-cineole, *n*-hexane + linalool at 298.15 K. For binary solutions of nitromethane with ethanol, propan-1-ol, propan-2-ol, butan-2-ol and 2-methyl-propan-2-ol, the values of rheochor increase with increase in composition of alkanol while it decreases for methanol + nitromethane. In the case of 1-propanol + DEGDEE and 1-propanol + DEGDBE, the values of rheochor increase with increase in mole fraction of 1-propanol. The values of rheochor decrease with increase in composition of *N*-methylacetamide for *N*-methylacetamide + 2-methoxyethanol and *N*-methylacetamide + water.

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References

1. H. Wang, W. Liu and J. Huang, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 2004, **36**, 743.

Note

2. C. H. Tu, S. L. Lee and I. H. Peng, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2001, **46**, 151.
3. M. M. H. Bhuiyan and K. Tamura, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 2004, **36**, 549.
4. A. S. Al-Jimaz, J. A. Al-Kandary and A. H. M. Abdul-Latif, *Fluid Phase Equilib.*, 2004, **218**, 247.
5. M. C. S. Subha, G. Narayana-Swamy, M. Eswari-Bai and K. S. V. Krishna-Rao, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 1876.
6. L. Mosteiro, E. Mascato, B. E. de Cominges, T. P. Iglesias and J. L. Legido, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 2001, **33**, 787.
7. J. Nath, Rashmi and R. Saini, *Fluid Phase Equilib.*, 1991, **68**, 281.
8. P. J. Victor and D. K. Hazra, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2002, **47**, 79.
9. F. Comelli, S. Ottani, R. Francesconi and C. Castellari, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2002, **47**, 93.
10. A. Pal and A. Kumar, *Indian Acad. Sci., J. Chem. Sci.*, 2004, **116**, 39.
11. C. H. Brown, M. Srebnik and P. V. Ramachandran, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1989, **54**, 1577.
12. W. Martindale, "The Extra Pharmacopolia", Pharmaceutical Press, London, 1989.
13. L. Grunberg and A. H. Nissan, *Nature (London)*, 1949, **164**, 799.
14. R. J. Fort and W. R. Moore, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1966, **62**, 1112.
15. K. Ramamoorthy, *J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1973, **11**, 554, 556.